

Molecular structure of an oxorhenium(V) '3+1' mixed ligand complex

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Abstract : Reaction of $[\text{Re}(\text{O})(\text{Cl})\{\eta^3\text{-(SCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}\}]$ with 3-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole in 1 : 2 molar proportion in acetonitrile gives rise to a red compound, $[\text{ReO}\{\eta^3\text{-(SCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}\}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})]$ (1). Subsequent crystallisation of it from a 1 : 1 mixture of acetonitrile and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) affords red crystals of 1.DMF. The X-ray structure shows that each molecule of the Re^{V} complex is connected to another nearest neighbouring Re^{V} complex via a DMF molecule with extensive hydrogen bonding. The complex displays a rare example of a 3D network involving all of the possible intermolecular hydrogen bonding and weak C-H $\cdots\pi$ interaction.

Keywords : Oxorhenium complex, supramolecular, crystal structure, '3+1' mixed ligands.

Introduction

In the last decade, sensational growth of technetium and rhenium chemistry reflects the continuously expanding application of important radio nuclides of these elements in external imaging ($^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$), diagnostic nuclear medicine or cancer radiotherapy ($^{186/188}\text{Re}$)¹⁻⁷. Development of radiopharmaceuticals as potential tumor imaging requires a viable synthetic pathway to prepare high energy beta emitters like ^{186}Re or ^{188}Re in a smooth and easy way. Amino-triazole and its various derivatives are used as medicinal drugs for different types of inhibitors. 1-amino-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole derivatives and 3-amino-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole derivatives are used respectively as aromatase inhibitors⁷ and catalase inhibitors⁷. Thus rhenium complex with an amino-triazole ligand is of contemporary interest in medicinal chemistry as well. Weak non-covalent interactions of the type hydrogen-bonding, aromatic-aromatic interactions, C-H $\cdots\pi$ interaction, cation $\cdots\pi$ interactions etc. have assumed great significance in chemistry, crystal engineering and biology⁸⁻¹¹. It is now realized that such types of interactions can work in a cooperative manner to stabilize liquids, crystals and mesophases. In this article, we describe the synthesis and structure of a novel Re^{V} complex with an amino-triazolethiolate ligand. The supramolecular topology is supported by an extensive network of hydrogen bonding and weak C-H $\cdots\pi$ interactions¹²⁻¹⁵.

Experimental

$\text{ReO}(\text{SSS})\text{Cl}$, where SSS = 3-thiapentane-1,5-dithiolate, was prepared following a reported procedure¹⁶. 3-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole was procured from Aldrich (USA). CH_3CN , DMF and CH_2Cl_2 were of analytical reagent grade and were used without further purification. C, H and N microanalyses were performed with a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyzer, FT-IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded with a Shimadzu FT-IR-8400S spectrophotometer and ESI mass spectra (in MeOH) on a Qtof Micro YA263 spectrometer.

Synthesis of $[\text{ReO}\{\eta^3\text{-(SCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{S}\}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})].\text{DMF}$ (1.DMF) : A solution of 3-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.047 g, 0.40 mmol) in CH_3CN (5 mL) was added dropwise, at room temperature, to a blue solution of $[\text{Re}(\text{O})\text{Cl}(\text{SSS})]$ (0.078 g, 0.20 mmol) in CH_3CN (10 mL). The mixture was stirred for 8 h in air to obtain a red precipitate. It was filtered and washed with CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL). The red solid product was dried under vacuum over silica gel. Yield, 0.095 g (87%) (Found : C, 19.22; H, 3.41; N, 12.73. $\text{ReC}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{S}_4\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 19.91; H, 3.35; N, 12.91%), IR (KBr) : ν 975 cm^{-1} (s, Re=O); 1678, 1682 (C=N); 3341, 3214, 2984 (NH_2), *m/z* 470 (1+ H^+). The product was crystallized from a 1 : 1 mixture of CH_3CN and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) to get block-shaped red crystals after several weeks. The crystals were suitable for the X-ray crystallography.

X-Ray crystallography :

Red block of complex **1.DMF** was mounted on a glass fiber. Intensity measurements were carried out on a Rigaku RAXIS RAPID image plate area detector system with Mo-K α radiation from a graphite monochromator ($\lambda = 0.71075 \text{ \AA}$) at a temperature of $-100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Crystal data collection and final refinement parameters are summarized in Table 1. The structures were solved by direct method (SIR-92)¹⁷ and expanded using Fourier techniques¹⁸. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. Hydrogen atoms were introduced at calculated positions using the riding model. All calculations were performed using the crystallographic software package^{19,20}.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for **1.DMF**

Empirical formula	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₂ ReS ₄
Formula weight	542.72
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c (14)
Unit cell dimensions :	
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.396(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	24.428(9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	9.685(3)
β (°)	106.94(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1673.8(1)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>T</i> (K)	173(1)
<i>D</i> _{calcd.} (g cm ⁻³)	2.153
<i>F</i> (000)	1048
λ (Mo K α) (Å)	0.71075
μ (mm ⁻¹)	7.771
Total data, unique data, <i>R</i> _{int}	16111, 3839, 0.049
Observed data [<i>I</i> > 2.0 σ (<i>I</i>)]	3839
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.99
<i>R</i> ₁ (<i>F</i> _o) ^a	0.028
<i>R</i> _w (<i>F</i> _o ²) ^b	0.075

$${}^a R_1 = \frac{\sum ||F_o| - |F_c||}{\sum |F_o|}, {}^b R_w = \left[\frac{\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2)}{\sum w(F_o^2)^2} \right]^{1/2}$$

Results and discussion

The ORTEP diagram with the atomic labelling scheme of **1.DMF** is shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond lengths and bond angles for **1.DMF** are given in Table 2. The central rhenium(V) ion is in a 'S₄O' chromophoric coordination environment. The four sulphur donors are not equiva-

Fig. 1. ORTEP drawing of complex **1.DMF** with the atomic numbering scheme. Thermal ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level. Hydrogen atoms were introduced in calculated positions.**Table 2.** Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg.) for complex **1.DMF**

Re1-O1	1.696(3)	Re1-S1	2.293(1)
Re1-S2	2.368(1)	Re1-S3	2.297(1)
Re1-S4	2.319(1)		
S1-Re1-S2	84.3(1)	S2-Re1-S3	84.4(2)
S1-Re1-S4	87.3(1)	S3-Re1-S4	80.7(1)
S1-Re1-O1	115.7(1)	S2-Re1-O1	102.1(1)
S3-Re1-O1	114.7(1)	S4-Re1-O1	105.6(1)
S1-Re1-S3	129.6(1)	S2-Re1-S4	152.0(3)
Re1-S4-C5	111.4(2)		

lent. They are of two types. The three S donors are of anionic thiolato type while the remaining one is neutral. The former three anionic sulphur sites are from two different ligands. SSS (3-thiapentane-1,5-dithiolate) provides two anionic and one neutral S. Triazole ligand imparts one thiolato sulphur. Thus the complex can aptly be described as a '3+1' mixed ligand complex. In order to delve into the geometry around Re^V center, we have taken recourse to the calculation of trigonality index, τ ^{21,22}. By definition $\tau = (\alpha - \beta)/60$, where α is the largest angle and β , the second largest angle around the central metal ion with the surrounded donor centres. Here Re^V=O is the central core and the donating sites are four S atoms. A zero value of τ indicates a regular square pyramidal geometry, while it is of unity in a perfectly trigonal

bipyramidal crystal field. Taking S2-Re1-S4 and S1-Re1-S3 angles are of $151.99(4)^\circ$ (α) and $129.55(5)^\circ$ (β), the value of τ comes out to be 0.37, which is in between 0 and 1. Thus the compound is distorted square pyramidal. The oxygen atom O(1) occupies the apical site of the square pyramid and is $1.696(3)$ Å apart from the Re^V centre. The Re=O and Re-S bond distances are in the usual ranges as observed for other well characterized pentacoordinate Re^V complexes¹⁶. Rhenium lies ~ 0.77 Å out of the average basal plane [Plane comprising S(1), S(2), S(3) and S(4)] of the distorted square pyramid towards the oxo group in 1. The dihedral angles of the ligand backbone, S1-C1-C2-S2 and S2-C3-C4-S4 are of $-51.7(4)^\circ$ and $54.5(3)^\circ$. In the crystal structure we can find four types of hydrogen bonding. Those types are illustrated as N_{amine}-H...N_{imine}, N_{imine}-H...N_{imine}, N_{amine}-H...O_{oxo} and O_{amide}...H-C (Figs. 2 and 3). Hydrogen bond distances for complex 1.DMF are given in Table 3. The complex molecule 1, itself involve intermolecular hydrogen bonding with neighboring units to self-assemble into a one-dimensional (1D) polymeric array. The specific interaction pattern of the self-complementary DMF molecule extent on the shape of hydrogen

Fig. 2. Supramolecular hydrogen bonding network in 1.DMF. Each molecule assembles with two nearest neighboring units with five hydrogen bonds. The hydrogen bonds are indicated by dotted lines.

Fig. 3. Illustration of the hydrogen bonding between a given DMF solvent molecule with neighboring units in the lattice. The hydrogen bonds are indicated by dotted lines.

Table 3. Intermolecular hydrogen bonds (Å, deg.) distance for complex 1.DMF

	D-H	D-A	D-H-A
N2-H16...N3	2.182(5)	2.855(5)	151.1(4)
N4-H17...N1	2.341(6)	3.054(6)	162.2(3)
N4-H18...O1	2.143(4)	3.018(6)	176.1(1)
C1-H2...O2	2.358(7)	3.146(7)	140.0(7)
C3-H6...O2	2.341(8)	3.213(8)	152.5(6)

bonded polymer to three-dimensional arrangement by using O_{amide}...H-C type of hydrogen bonding with two rectangular neighbors of Re-complex molecules with each molecule of DMF. Weak C-H... π interactions²³ (3.575 Å) are also operative between the methyl group of DMF and triazole moiety in 1.DMF. Extension of this intercalated DMF molecule in this binding pattern throughout the crystal results in a corrugated two-dimensional layers parallel to the xy plane (Figs. 4, 5).

In summary, a novel five-coordinate Re^V complex has been synthesised and characterised successfully. Importantly, the title complex contains functional group (-NH₂) and structural motifs capable of favouring weak C-H... π interaction and hydrogen bonded network that cooperatively support supramolecular architecture. From functional view point, the complex may be a potential radio-pharmaceutical since the free -NH₂ terminal can be tagged with a peptide residue.

Fig. 4. View of the crystal structure down the crystal c-axis.

Fig. 5. The corrugated two-dimensional layer arrangement of DMF molecule in crystal structure down the c-axis. Re-complex molecule is omitted for clarity.

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